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The Implementation Of Nomadic Education Program In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The nomadic education programme is designed to educate nomads through special effort because they have been lagging behind in this direction. However, some factors are impeding to the success of its proper implementations. This study examined factors influencing the implementation of nomadic education programme in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The objectives were to find out the effect of funding on provision of infrastructures and instructional facilities on the implementation of nomadic education programme; to examine the extent to which staffing affects the implementation of nomadic education programme and the impact of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme. A cross-sectional survey research design was used to gather detailed of information from respondents. Two research instruments were used to collect data for the study namely: Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQ) and Interview Guide. Reliability of FINEQ was established with the use of test-retest reliability value of 0.83 and validity was determined through face and content validity with a CVI value of 0.90. One hundred and seventy (170) questionnaires were administered to respondents in the three (3) randomly selected primary schools in WamakkoLGA, Sokoto State. However, one hundred and sixty eight (168) questionnaires were returned. The major findings of this study are that there is a high influence of funding of provision of infrastructures and instructional facilities, a high influence of staffing and a high impact of teachers' supervision in nomadic primary schools on the implementation of nomadic education programme. Based on these findings, it is recommended that governments at all levels (local, state and federal) should give appropriate and enough funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities; government should ensure adequate and qualified staffing, and teachers should be punctual and regular in the nomadic primary schools; and supervisors from Education Inspectorates of local, state and federal as well as parents and community leadership should have more time to visit the activities in these nomadic primary schools.

Keywords: nomadic education programme, instructional facilities, staffing

INTRODUCTION

Education for all is the responsibility and right of all mankind (Alkali, 1988). Greater commitment to the universalization of access to basic education has heightened interest in the provision of quality basic education to nomadic and other educationally disadvantaged groups in Nigeria. These segments of the population have serious limitations to equitable access to basic education through the conventional education system as a result of certain occupational and socio-cultural peculiarities. Out of the estimated 9.3 million nomadic peoples in Nigeria comprising pastoralists and migrant fishing groups, about 3.1 million are children of school age (Tahir, 2008). The participation of the nomads in the existing formal and non-formal basic education programs is abysmally low, with literacy rates ranging between 0.2% and 2.0% (Tahir, 2008).

According to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2009), the major constraints to participation of nomads in formal and non-formal education are their migratory movements in search of water and pasture, the centrality of child labour in their production system, the irrelevance of the school curriculum which is tailored to meet the educational needs of sedentary groups; and their physical isolation since they operate in mostly inaccessible physical environments.

Therefore, this explains why a special educational provision is made for the nomads, since they have had little or no access to formal and non-formal education. It is the wisdom of government that Nomadic Education Programme is designed to provide an unfettered access to education for nomadic groups in Nigeria (Ezeomah, 1988).

Statement of the Problem

The United Nations' 1984 Universal Declaration on Human Rights state that "everyone has the right to education". The government of Nigeria has committed itself to literacy enhancement of the Fulani. The National Policy on Education (2004) stresses that education is the birth right of every child, and education should be brought close to the environment of the child. The policy enjoins that whenever possible, arrangements will be made for such children to assist their parents in the morning and go to school in the evening. Special and adequate inducement will be provided to teachers in rural areas to make them stay in the job (NPE, 2004).

The nomadic education programme has a multifaceted schooling arrangement to suit the diverse transhuman habits of the Fulani. Different agencies are involved in the educational process. They work together to offer effective school system where the schools and the teachers move with the Fulani children.

The uncertainties of the movement of the Fulani make educational planning and student monitoring difficult. Unscheduled out-migration due to environmental failures or conflicts between the farmers and the pastoral Fulani disrupts school operations and classroom composition. Lack of appropriate use of funding forces the government to rely on volunteers or unqualified teachers. The poor salaries cannot attract the calibre of staff with the commitment to educational enrichment of the Fulani. Scarcity of chalks, books, pencils, and blackboards. Requests from schools for children to bring learning kits dampen the spirit of parents who think they have already made enough sacrifices by letting their children go to school rather than go on grazing (Sokoto Report, 2012).

Objectives

- i. Find out the extent to which funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities affects the implementation of nomadic education programme.
- ii. Examine the extent to which staffing affects the implementation of nomadic education programme.

Research questions

- i. To what extent does the funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities affects the implementation of nomadic education programme?
- ii. To what extent does staffing affects the implementation of nomadic education programme?

Research Hypotheses

- i. Funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities does not significantly affect the

- implementation of nomadic education programme.
- ii. Staffing does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education programme.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology that the study followed. It focused on the research design, study area, population, sample size, sampling techniques and procedure, data collection instruments, methods of testing the validation of instruments and methods of data analysis used in conducting the study.

Research Design

The research design as explained by Kinner and Taylor (1981) is the basic plan, which guides the data collection and analysis phase of the research project. It is also the framework, which specifies the type of information to be collected, the sources of data and data collection procedure. In addition research design gives the detailed plan of what data to gather, from whom, how and when to collect data, and how to analyse the data obtained (Paulin, 2007). In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used a cross-sectional survey research design because the samples were drawn from different levels of respondents, as maintained by Creswell (2012). The researcher used students, teachers, headmasters, parents and nomadic community leaders as respondents.

Population of the Study

The target population of this study covered all the three (3) nomadic primary schools in Wamakko local government area recognised by the Sokoto State Agency for Nomadic Education (SSANE), Ministry of Education, Sokoto as at the time of this study. The schools are: Fandirma, Diddiba and Runjin Biyo Nomadic Primary Schools. Table 3.1 shows the population of the entire people living in the area including students, teachers, parents and communities’ leaders in Nomadic area of Wamakko Local Government Area. The total population as at the time of carrying out this research was twenty two thousand, five hundred and ninety one (22,591) people with two hundred and seventeen (217) students, twenty (20) teachers, one hundred and sixty four (164) parents and thirteen (13) communities’ leaders.

Table 1:Nomadic Population in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria

S/ N	NOMADIC AREA	POPULATION	Communities leaders	Nomadic school	No of Teachers	No. of Students	No of Parents
1	Fandirma	7,578	4	School A	4	65	53
2	Diddiba	8,560	5	School B	13	83	64
3	Runjin Biyo	6,453	4	School C	3	69	47
	Total	22,591	13		20	217	164

Source: Wamakko L.G.E.A.(2024)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size was calculated or determined using a simplified formula given by Krejcie and Morgan (1970).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size and e = 5% (0.05) is the level of significance. Purposive and simple random samplings were used to select key respondents (students, teachers, head teachers, parents and community leader) considering the fact that they are the subjects under investigation. Community leaders, parents and head teachers were selected using purposive sampling

while students and teachers were selected using simple random sampling to allow each of them to have equal representation for the study.

Table 2: Population and Sample for the study

Catgry. of the Respondents	Population size	Sample size	Sampling Technique
Head Teachers	3	3	Purposive sampling
Teachers	17	16	Simple random sampling
Students	217	170	Simple random sampling
Parent	164	20	Convenient sampling
Leaders	13	13	Purposive sampling
Total	414	222	

Source: Researcher's field survey (2024)

Method of Data Collection

This study employed the use of two research instruments namely; questionnaire and interview.

Instrumentation

The major instrument used for data collection in this study is questionnaire given in Appendix I. The researcher administered questionnaires to selected respondents (students, teachers and head teachers), conducted interview with some community leaders and parents. This is because questionnaire enables the respondents to freely express their views and opinions concerning the topic as long as they could read and write. Questionnaires were constructed such that all the information pertaining to the study obtained using close ended items.

The questionnaire used was named Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQT). Items in this questionnaire were categorised into four sections A, B, C and D each section excluding section A, contains 10 four Likert-scale items questions. Section A was the preliminary section which sought respondents' basic information, section B contains questionnaire items that dealt with funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on implementation of nomadic education programme, section C consists of items on the effects of staffing on nomadic education programme while section D is deals with the impacts of supervision on nomadic education programme. Funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on implementation of nomadic education programme,

The factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQS) was also used for the students which has only two sections. Section A was the preliminary section which sought students' basic information. And section B contains dichotomous items that dealt with entirety of students' functions in nomadic education programme.

Based on Table 1.2, 170 students, 116 teachers and 3 head teachers were provided with questionnaires.

Validity and Reliability of research instruments

Content validity

Content validity was used to determine the validity of the self-constructed Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQ). The researcher distributed

copies of the questionnaire to experts competent in the field Nomadic education programme for their contribution. The advantage of this validity type is to determine the extent to which the items of the construct represent the concept to be measured (Creswell, 2012). Content Validity Index (CVI) of the construct determined the validity of the both students and teachers questionnaires.

CVI for teachers/head-teachers questionnaire can be obtained by computing

$$CVI = \frac{\text{Number of items rated as relevant}}{\text{Total number of items in the scale}} = \frac{29}{32} = 0.90$$

While for students questionnaire $CVI = \frac{\text{Number of items rated as relevant}}{\text{Total number of items in the scale}} = \frac{16}{20} = 0.80$

The content validity index was 0.90 and 0.8 implying that the questionnaire was 90% and 80% valid for teachers and students questionnaire respectively.

Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the reliability of the instrument Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQ), copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the Teachers, head-teachers and students and their responses were recorded in SPSS software and computed using Cronbach alpha. The purpose of Cronbach alpha is to test for internal consistency of an instrument (Cronbach, 1984). The tables below (table 3.3) indicate the total reliability of the instrument and the reliability of each construct. The reliability was found to be .842 for teachers' questionnaire and .821 for students questionnaire implying that the questionnaires were 84.2% and 82.1% reliable respectively. It was also found that each construct of the instrument was reliable and no item needs to be deleted (*Cronbach's Alpha if item Deleted* <.842).

Table 3. Reliability Statistics

Instruments	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Teachers/Head-teachers FINEQ	.842	29
Students FINEQ	.821	16

Source : Field Study (2024)

RESULTS FOR DATA ANALYSIS

Research question one: *To what extent does funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities affect the implementation of nomadic education programme?*

Table 4.8: Teachers' responses on the funding of provision of nomadic school infrastructures and instructional materials

Table 4.1 Adequate provision of funds for nomadic education programme

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The fund provided under nomadic education program is quite enough for the programme	Frequency	4	1	0	12	17
	Percent (%)	23.5	5.9	0.0	70.6	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Most of the teachers numbering 12 (70.6%) strongly disagreed with the adequate provision of funds for nomadic education while 4 teachers representing only 29.4% of the teachers agreed with the adequate funding in nomadic education. This result therefore showed that there is no enough funding for nomadic education in Wamakko local government.

Table 4.2 Appropriate budget of for nomadic programme

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The fund is well budgeted for nomadic programme in this area	Frequency	3	0	10	4	17
	Percent (%)	17.6	0.0	58.8	23.5	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Although teachers claimed inadequate provision of fund in nomadic education, and even the available provision according to the 14 (82.3) of the teachers was not well budgeted while 3 (17.6%) of teachers agreed that the funding was adequately budgeted. This therefore meant the little funding provided was not well budgeted for nomadic education in Wamakko local government.

4.3 Effective utilizations of funds in nomadic programme

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The utilizations of funds in nomadic programme is quite impressive	Frequency	4	1	0	12	17
	Percent (%)	23.5	5.9	0.0	70.6	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

The result in the above table shows that 12 (70.6%) of the teachers disagreed that the little budgeted funding for nomadic education was being effectively utilised. Only 5 representing 29.4% of the teachers were impressive with the way the nomadic funds were being utilized. This result therefore shows that funds were not being effectively utilised for nomadic education in Wamakko local government.

On the utilisation of funds provision of physical structure for nomadic education 13 (76.4%) of teachers disagreed that funds were utilised properly while 4 (23.5%) of teachers agreed with the funds utilisation of funds for this reason. This result therefore showed that funds were not utilised on the utilisation of funds provision of physical structure for nomadic education in Wamakko local government area

Table 4.4: Means ranking of teachers' responses to the funding of provision of nomadic school infrastructures and instructional materials

Items for teachers (n=17)	Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
The fund provided under nomadic education program is quite enough for the programme	2.40	Moderate influence	1
The fund is well budgeted for nomadic programme in this area	1.70	Low influence	8
The utilizations of funds in nomadic programme is quite impressive	1.10	Low influence	9
The fund enable the provision of all required instructional facilities	1.05	Low influence	10
There is adequate funding from federal State and local governments Boards.	2.21	Moderate influence	5
Infrastructure such as provision of classroom and classroom furniture are adequately provided.	2.35	Moderate influence	2
Schools and classrooms are frequently Renovated and rehabilitated	2.28	Moderate influence	3
Nomads are adequately provided with scholastic learning materials such as textbooks, exercise books	2.10	Moderate influence	7
Availability of instructional materials is also common in most nomadic school here	2.23	Moderate influence	4
School libraries and books have been provided	2.18	Moderate influence	6
Average Mean	1.67	Low influence	

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Table 4.4 shows the means ranking of responses for the funding of provision of nomadic school infrastructures and instructional materials. It is observed that among the measures, the fund provided for nomadic education programme is quite enough (mean of 2.40) is the most prominent. This is followed by infrastructure such as provision of classroom and classroom furniture is adequate (mean of 2.35). The least measure of influence is the fund enable the provision of all the required instructional facilities (mean of 1.05). Overall, there is a low influence of provision of nomadic school infrastructures and instructional facilities (with overall mean of 1.67). Therefore, funding for infrastructures and instructional materials in nomadic primary schools has low influence on the implementation of nomadic primary schools in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria

4. 5 Adequate Classroom and furniture

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Do you have enough classrooms and furniture?	Frequency	6	162	168
	Percent (%)	3.6	96.4	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Most of the students numbering 168 (96.4%) claimed that there is no adequate classrooms and furniture in their schools while 6 teachers representing only 3.6% of the students answered that they had been provided. This result therefore showed that there is no enough classroom and furniture in most schools for nomadic education in Wamakko local government.

4. 6 Adequate reading and writing materials

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Do you have enough text and exercises books for all subjects?	Frequency	6	162	168
	Percent (%)	3.6	96.4	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

On the provision of adequate reading and writing materials in nomadic education 162 (96.4%) of students claimed that they had not been provided with adequate reading and writing materials in their schools while 6 (3.6%) of students admitted to had been provided with the materials. This result therefore showed that adequate reading and writing materials were not provided for students in nomadic education programme of Wamakko local government area.

Research Hypothesis One: Funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities does not significantly affect the implementation of nomadic education programme.

In order to ascertain significant effect of funding for provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on the implementation of nomadic education programme, the above result was analysed using chi-square statistical tool. Table 4.11 below presents the result obtained.

Table 4.7: Chi-square test for significant effect of funding for provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on the implementation of nomadic education programme

Computed statistic	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Chi-Square	97.451	17	.001
Likelihood Ratio	103.521	17	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	81.521	17	.001
N of Valid Cases	168		

Source: Result of the analysis (2024)

Results presented in table 4.11 shows the χ^2 value for significant effect of funding for provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on the implementation of nomadic education programmes 97.451 (p-value= 0.001 < 0.05), therefore the null hypothesis Funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities does not significantly affect the implementation of nomadic education programme was rejected. This indicated that there is statistically significant effect of funding for provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on the implementation of nomadic education programme. Hence, it was concluded that funding has low influence on the implementation of nomadic education programme in those secondary schools.

This study found out that fund provided under nomadic education programme was not quite enough for the programme, fund was not well budgeted for nomadic programme in the area, utilizations of funds in nomadic programme was not quite impressive, fund could not enable the provision of all required instructional facilities, inadequate funding from federal, state and local governments' boards, infrastructures such as provision of classroom and classroom furniture were inadequate, schools and classrooms were not frequently renovated and rehabilitated, nomads were not adequately provided with scholastic learning materials such as textbooks and exercise books, unavailability of instructional materials, and school libraries and books were not provided in most nomadic schools.

Finding also showed that among the measures, the fund provided under nomadic education programme was not quite enough is the most prominent factor followed by infrastructure such as provision of classroom and classroom furniture being not adequate while the least measure of influence is the fund being not enough for the provision of all the required instructional facilities. Overall, there is a high influence of provision of nomadic school infrastructures and instructional facilities. Therefore, funding of provision of infrastructures and instructional materials in nomadic primary schools has influence on the implementation of nomadic primary schools in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Also, finding indicated these nomadic schools did not have enough classrooms in their schools, no adequate furniture for all students in class, no enough text books for all subjects and no enough exercise books, pencil and books.

These findings are not different from the responses given by the parents and community leaders during the interview and focus group. They confirmed that:

“it is the government that provide fund for nomadic education in the area but the funds provided by the government were not enough for the programme. In the nomadic schools, new classes were not constructed and old ones were not renovated. There was no adequate furniture in the nomadic schools”.

They further confirmed that:

“Parents do not raise fund for their children education. Their children were not provided with text books and exercise books by government but few of the parent provide. There were no libraries and books in the nomadic schools”.

4.4 Research question two: What are the influences of staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme?

Table 4.12: Teachers' responses on the staffing and implementation of nomadic education programme, Adequate, sufficient and competent teachers for nomadic education

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
There are enough sufficient competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic education	Frequency	4	0	10	3	17
	Percent (%)	23.5	0.0	58.8	17.6	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

The result in the above table shows that 13 (76.4%) of the teachers disagreed on adequate, sufficient and competent teachers for nomadic education nomadic education were provided. And only 4 representing (23.5%) of the teachers were agreed with the provision of adequate, sufficient and competent teachers for

nomadic education. This result therefore shows that Adequate, sufficient and competent teachers were not provided for nomadic education in Wamakko local government.

Regular attendance of classes by the nomadic teachers

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The teachers are regularly attending classes and they are doing well	Frequency	4	0	9	4	17
	Percent (%)	23.5	0.0	52.9	23.5	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

On the regular attendance of classes by the nomadic teachers for nomadic education 13 (76.4%) of teachers disagreed that they regularly attend classes while 4 (23.5%) of teachers said they regularly attend classes. This result therefore showed that teachers were not regularly attending classes in nomadic school of Wamakko local government area.

Prompt payment of teachers' salary for motivation and encouragement

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Teachers in nomadic programme are well motivated and encouraged by paying teachers salary promptly	Frequency	4	0	4	9	17
	Percent (%)	23.5	0.0	23.5	52.9	100.0

Source:Results of the analysis (2024)

On the teachers motivation and encouragement which include prompt payment of salaries and other liabilities 13 (76.4%) of teachers disagreed they were being paid promptly while 4 (23.5%) of teachers admitted to have prompt payment and encouragement. This result therefore showed that the teachers were not adequately motivated or encouraged for nomadic education in Wamakko local government area.

Timely Teacher professional development such as organizing workshops and seminar

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Teacher professional development such as organizing workshops and seminar are greatly frequently undertaken	Frequency	1	3	6	7	17
	Percent (%)	5.6	17.6	35.3	41.2	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Results from table 4.12 showed that majority (76.5%)of the teachers disagreed that there were enough competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic schools, that teachers are regularly attending classes and they are doing well, that teachers in nomadic schools are well motivated and encouraged by paying their salary promptly; and that most teachers have minimum teaching qualification of N.C.E while 23.5% agreed on these issues. Majority (70.6%)of the teachers disagreed that most of the teachers are not nomads while 29.4% of them agreed. About 64.7% disagreed that most of the teachers posted by government from far while 35.3% agreed. Similarly, majority (76.5%)of teachers disagreed that teacher professional development such as organizing workshops and seminar are greatly frequently undertaken while 23.5% agreed on this issue.

The majority of the responses indicated that staffing was not adequate for the nomadic education programme in the community.

Table 4.13: Means of teachers' views on the responses of staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme

Items for teachers (n=17)	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
There are enough sufficient competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic education	2.56	High influence	1
The teachers are regularly attending classes and they are doing well	1.72	Low influence	7
Teachers in nomadic programme are well motivated and encouraged by paying teachers salary promptly	1.78	Moderate influence	6
Most Teachers in nomadic education have minimum teaching qualification of N.C.E	2.38	Moderate influence	4
Most of the teachers are not nomads	1.90	Moderate influence	5
Most of the teachers posted by government from far	2.49	Moderate influence	2
Teacher professional development such as organizing workshops and seminar are greatly frequently undertaken	2.41	Moderate influence	3
Average Mean	1.69	Low influence	

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Table 4.13 shows the means of teachers' views on the influence of staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme. It is observed that among the measures, having enough competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic schools (mean of 2.56) is the most prominent. This is followed by having most of the teachers posted by government from far (mean of 2.52). The least measure of influence is teachers not regularly attending classes and doing well (mean of 1.72). Overall, there is a low influence of staffing in nomadic primary schools on the implementation of this nomadic education programme (mean of 1.69).

Table 4.14: Students' responses on the staffing and implementation of nomadic education programme
Students' attendance to the classes in nomadic schools

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Do you attend class regularly?	Frequency	150	13	168
	Percentage (%)	89.3	7.7	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

On the regular attendance of classes by the nomadic students, 150 (89.3%) of students claimed to be attending the school regularly while 12 (7.7%) of students admitted to dodged schools or attend classes regularly. This result therefore showed that students were regularly attending classes in nomadic school of Wamakko local government area.

Availability of teacher in nomadic education classes

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Do you have enough teachers for all students?	Frequency	6	162	168
	Percentage (%)	3.6	96.4	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Despite the attendance of schools by majority of nomadic students most of the students numbering 162 (96.4%) said that there were no available teachers to attend to them while 6 representing only 3.6% of the

students answered that the teachers were available. This result therefore showed that there are no enough teachers in most schools for nomadic education in Wamakko local government

Table 4.15: Teachers' ability to communicate well in nomadic class

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Do you understand what you are studying at school?	Frequency	72	96	168
	Percentage (%)	42.9	57.1	100.0

Source:Results of the analysis (2024)

On the issue of students ability to understand teachers communication 96 (57.1%) studentsdeclined their ability to understand teaches communication while 72students representing only 42.9% answered that they understood teachers' communication. This result therefore showed that not all students comprehensively understand their teachers' communication. This may be due to the language barrier or teachers incompetency in most schools for nomadic education in Wamakko local government

Teachers-pupil interaction in nomadic schools

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Are you happy with what your teacher thought you at school?	Frequency	4	164	168
	Percentage (%)	2.4	97.6	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Result in table 4.14 shows students' responses based on the staffing in their schools. Overwhelming majority of the students (97.0%) were not attending class regularly, 96.4% said that they were not having enough teachers, 97.0% disagreed that their teachers were regularly attending classes, 57.1% could not understand what they were studying at school and 97.6% were not happy with what teachers thought them at school.

Hypothesis Two: Staffing does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education programme.

In order to ascertain the effect of staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme, the above results were analysed using chi-square statistical tool. Table 4.15 below presents the result generated.

Table 4.18: Chi-square test for effect of Staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme

Computed statistic	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Chi-Square	52.514	17	.000
Likelihood Ratio	63.105	17	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	12.626	17	.002
N of Valid Cases	168		

Source: Result of the analysis (2024)

Result presented in table 4.15 shows the χ^2 value for the effect of staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme as 52.514 and pvalue = 0.000 < 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis which stated that staffing does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education programme was rejected. And this showed that there is statistically significant effect of staffing on the implementation of nomadic education programme. Hence, it is concluded that staffing has low influence on the implementation in those nomadic schools

The finding from this study showed that there was lack of competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic schools, teachers were not regularly attending classes, they were not doing well, teachers in nomadic schools were not being motivated and encouraged as salaries not paid promptly; and that most teachers do not have minimum teaching qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). Similarly, it was

found out that most of the teachers are not nomads and posted by government from far. Also, teacher professional development such as organizing workshops and seminar were not frequently undertaken. Finding further showed that among the measures, not having enough competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic schools is the most prominent influence in the implementation of nomadic education programme. This was followed by having most of the teachers posted by government from far. The least measure of influence is teachers not regularly attending classes and not doing well. Overall, there is a low influence of staffing in nomadic primary schools on the implementation of this nomadic education programme.

Finding from students' responses based on the staffing in their schools showed that they were not attending class regularly, not having enough teachers, that their teachers were not regularly attending classes, could not understand what they were studying at school and were not happy with what teachers thought them at school.

The community leaders and parents during the interview and focus group further confirmed these findings and said that:

“There were no enough and sufficient staffs for the programme, but even the few available ones were not regularly attending classes. Teachers were not well motivated and encouraged by prompt payments of salaries. Most teachers in the nomadic schools do not have minimum teaching qualification of NCE as prescribed by national policy of education and teachers professional development such as workshops were not frequently being organised”.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATION

- 1) Based on the findings, the study concluded that fund provided under nomadic education programme was not quite enough for the programme, fund was not well budgeted for nomadic programme in the area of study, utilizations of funds in nomadic programme was not quite impressive, fund could not enable the provision of all required instructional facilities, inadequate funding from federal, state and local governments' boards, infrastructures such as provision of classroom and classroom furniture were inadequate, schools and classrooms were not frequently renovated and rehabilitated, nomads were not adequately provided with scholastic learning materials such as textbooks and exercise books, unavailability of instructional materials, and school libraries and books were not provided in most nomadic schools.
- 2) Teachers posted to teach in nomadic school slack competency, not regularly attending classes, not doing well, not being motivated and encouraged as salaries not paid promptly; and that most teachers do not have minimum teaching qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). Similarly, it was concluded that most of the teachers are not nomads but posted by government from far. Also, teacher professional development such as organizing workshops and seminar were not frequently undertaken. On the part of students, attendance in class was not regular but claimed that their schools lack enough teachers and the few ones available are not regularly teaching them. They also claimed further of not understanding the lessons at school and not being happy with what teachers teach them at school. Among the factors considered in respect of staffing in nomadic schools, not having enough competent teachers posted to teach in nomadic schools is the most prominent influence in the implementation of nomadic education programme. This was followed by having most of the teachers posted by government from far. The least factor of influence is teachers not regularly attending classes and not doing well. Overall, there is a low influence of staffing in nomadic primary schools on the implementation of the nomadic education programme in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto state, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATION

- (i) Government should give appropriate and enough funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities for the implementation of nomadic education programme to be successful.

- (ii) Government should ensure adequate and qualified staffing, and teachers should be punctual and regular in the nomadic primary schools.

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